

Case Report

Complications in the diagnosis of Sars-CoV-2 disease (Covid-19) in fully vaccinated patients. Homicide by omission.

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Abstract

A former colleague, vaccinated twice with an mRNA vaccine in compliance with all guidelines, developed a sore throat, malaise, and aching limbs 5 months after the second dose (with enough, just minimally decreased neutralizing antibodies just before infection), which turned into a dry cough and other clinically relevant symptoms within 24 hours. Three of four PCR and/or RT-PCR tests were negative, as were four of five antigen tests of different reputable manufacturers.

After an intensive search and consultation of an external colleague, the reason was found: a small focus of Sars-CoV-2 in the right sinus in a case of reduced ventilation due to a slightly curved nasal septum. With clearing the local virus cluster the patient began to recover slowly. Consequence: in persistent mild Covid-19 disease, even in vaccinated patients, focal viral reservoirs should be searched for as they might play a role in "long Covid" as well.

Case

About five months after an effective Covid-19 vaccination (mRNA) (sufficient neutralizing antibodies in both, NAb and IgG PoC tests) a caucasian-mediterranean male (46) developed a sore throat, aching limbs, malaise, mood changes and a dry cough, followed by deterioration of a preexisting neurological illness. Several antigen tests for health professionals marketed by Roche, Abbott and local brands remained strictly negative. Only the NADAL rapid test (European marketing name for a product made in Mainland China) delivered a positive signal. The only other member of the household was also tested. This individual's NADAL antigen test for health professionals (also vaccinated with an mRNA vaccine, however, with a more recent booster shot) was negative on NADAL at day two of the patient's symptoms, weak positive in day three and back to NADAL-negative on day four without any symptoms at all times. Due to local legislation he went into quarantine nevertheless.

Due to the patient's clinical situation he decided for himself to follow the FLCCC MATH-I protocol (status Sep 25, 2021) with additional budesonid inhalation powder 2x0,4 mg/day on top. The patient responded relatively well to this therapy, in particular the persistent dry cough improved at a high-dose steroid therapy with budesonide.^{1,3,7} In order to get immediate access to a PCR test the patient chose a private (licensed, but not covered by his health insurance) station near his home. There a highly inadequate swab test of the throat was performed (the patient is a physician himself and experienced in taking swab tests) with a

negative PCR result. He gave this test station a second chance, however, the sample was taken grossly inadequately again. The result negative once more. A third PCR (RT-PCR) was performed at a nearby international airport, located there to allow individuals with a negative test to board an intercontinental flight. Even at this site the swab test was below standard, the test came back - no surprise - as negative. Nevertheless, the clinically ill and violently coughing patient could have taken any flight he wanted within the following 48 hours.

Why all but one antigen (Ag) test did not react will remain a mystery since it is difficult to impossible to obtain data from these companies. The reason might be found in the fact that most, if not all tests of this kind which are sold under a European brand name, are just re-labeled products made in Korean, Vietnam Mainland China, India etc.; a fact the European resellers try to hide.^{2,3} Therefore it is difficult to impossible to get the information which would be essential.

Since the more or less semi-quantitative results of his neutralizing antibody test began to produce different signals (semi-quantitative aspects are mentioned in the leaflet of the test without further specification), it was important to find out what these signals and the isolated positive results of the NADAL antigen test meant. Especially since the patient's health situation deteriorated with neuropsychiatric symptoms like mood swings, agitation, etc.^{1,3,5,7} With the help of the Lazar Research Team a protocol was set up, with the outcome indicating, beyond a shadow of a doubt, that the results of the NADAL test were by no means erratic but dependent on the disinfection and/or ventilation of the right posterior sinus region of the patient. Once having disinfected this small area the test became almost negative. After about 4 to 6 hours it gradually turned into a positive test again. After 8 hours the tests was entirely positive once more. This could be repeated numerous times, always with the same result. (These outcomes were consistent with that of an orderly performed PCR test in a regional tertiary reference lab.)¹⁰

Conclusion

This interesting case which was not adequately diagnosed by several third parties teaches us some import aspects in the middle of this pandemic:²⁻⁹

1. Quite obviously, negative Sars-CoV-2 tests (PCR and antigen/Ag) should be considered as possibly false as long the patient has typical Covid symptoms.
2. The latter is less true for positive tests as symptom-free cases are common.
3. Point one is also true for "fully vaccinated" individuals.

4. The bio-physical rationale behind all test assays, both for labs as well as for point-of-care and home tests has to become more transparent.
5. The quality of the personnel in all test stations has to be drastically improved and strictly monitored.
6. The sinuses and all their adjacent structures might play a role as a safe haven for the Sars-CoV-2 virus, possibly as a contributing factor to “long Covid”.

We had to come to the conclusion that anecdotal sloppiness in “Covid tests” is not a rare phenomenon. In many cases major companies seem to design the test-infrastructure in a way that only most severely ill patients with a high viral load will be tested positive.^{3,6,7,8,9} The official information policy towards the physicians in most western countries is a disgrace, patients are left alone in this multimillion Dollar business. Airlines that test their own passengers fit to board their planes by well-adjusted test procedures (as could have happened in our case) are criminals with uniforms, wings and tomato juice.

Sloppy performed throat swabs plus barely half an inch nasal swabs have never proven to work in real life, but they have become the standard in many countries, especially in the private sector. Especially vaccinated individuals with no or mild symptoms can be highly dangerous virus carriers, biological ammunition on legs. Orderly, deep, and painful nasopharyngeal swabs plus throat swabs with a second swab stick should be made mandatory until fully independent research will have clarified which role local Sars-CoV-2 reservoirs in recovered and vaccinated patients might play. Whoever wants to take a flight, enjoy a movie or visit a club has to understand that the “pain” of a professionally done nasopharyngeal swab is nothing in comparison to a covid infection.

Everything else than much higher standards we consider homicide by omission or stinginess.

Conflicts of interest.

None declared.

Ethics and legal

This paper is in conformity with all relevant treaties and agreements.

Literature

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10. On Thursday, September 2nd, 2021 the lab informed the patient and the physician responsible for the test that a technical issue had occurred and the positive PCR was most likely negative in reality. The patient refused to repeat the test.

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